

Current Situation of Ho Chi Minh Ethics in Revolutionary Ethics Education and Training

for Party Members Of Can Tho City, Vietnam

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Abstract: Ethical education for cadres and party members is a major policy of all countries and peoples in the world. Ho Chi Minh, the great leader of the Vietnamese people, throughout his life of revolutionary activities, always set a shining moral example of a revolutionary, wholeheartedly striving and sacrificing for the people, for the country, for the nation. Ho Chi Minh considered ethics to be the foundation, the root of a revolutionary, the strength of a revolutionary, considering it the root of a tree, the source of a river. A revolutionary must have revolutionary ethics as a foundation in order to complete the glorious revolutionary mission for the cause of national independence and socialism. The article analyzes the current situation of applying Ho Chi Minh's moral thought in educating and training revolutionary ethics for cadres and party members, on that basis, proposes a number of solutions to improve the effectiveness of applying Ho Chi Minh's moral thought in educating and training revolutionary ethics for cadres and party members of the Can Tho City Party Committee in the new period.

INTRODUCTION

President Ho Chi Minh (1890-1969) [1, 2, p. 241] - is the father, the Vietnamese nation's leader (the Uncle) [3, p. 433-466], is a great revolutionary,

who is not only the soul of the Vietnamese revolution, "a master political strategist", a "great man of culture" [4, p. 135], and an outstanding hero, a fervent revolutionary communist soldier [5], a great Vietnamese educator, a man of talent and integrity. Ho Chi Minh always set a shining moral example of a revolutionary, wholeheartedly striving and sacrificing for the people, for the country, for the nation. Ho Chi Minh considered morality to be the foundation, the root of a revolutionary, the strength of a revolutionary, considering it the root of a tree, the source of a river. A revolutionary must have revolutionary morality as a foundation in order to complete the glorious revolutionary mission for the cause of national independence and socialism. He wrote: "Just like a river must have a source to have water, without a source the river will dry up. A tree must have roots, without roots the tree will wither. A revolutionary must have ethics, without ethics, no matter how talented he is, he cannot lead the people" [6, p.292]. "All successes or failures are due to good or bad cadres. Cadres are the root of all work, so training cadres is the root of the Party" [6, p.280]. During his lifetime, Ho Chi Minh paid great attention to promoting the practice of revolutionary ethics for Vietnamese people, especially educating, cultivating, and training revolutionary ethics for cadres and party members. During his revolutionary career, Ho Chi Minh gave many speeches and articles to educate and train revolutionary ethics for cadres, party members, and our people. Before passing away, he left a Will, advising: "Every party member and cadre must be truly imbued with revolutionary ethics, truly frugal, honest, impartial and selfless" [7, p.611].

Realizing the importance of revolutionary ethics of cadres and party members. At the 2nd Congress (1951), our Party affirmed: The current political line, working style and revolutionary ethics of our Party are the line, style and ethics of President Ho Chi Minh, etc. The entire Party should strive to study the political line, style and revolutionary ethics of President Ho Chi Minh. At the 7th Congress (1991), the Party affirmed and solemnly recorded in the Party Document: "The Party takes Marxism-Leninism and Ho Chi Minh's thought as the ideological foundation and guideline for action" [8, p.127]. The Politburo issued Directive 03-CT/TW on "Continuing to promote studying and following the moral example of Ho Chi Minh". The 12th Politburo issued Directive 05-CT/TW on "Promoting studying and following the ideology, morality and style of Ho Chi Minh". Continuing the spirit of previous Congresses, the 13th Congress (2021) of our Party has always focused on the issue: "Promoting the study and following of Ho Chi Minh's ideology, morality and lifestyle according to Directive No. 05-CT/TW of the Politburo has become an important and regular task of each Party organization and cadres and Party members have had many new and creative ways of doing things, achieving positive results" [9, pp. 176-177]. Conclusion No. 01-KL/TW of the 13th Politburo on continuing to implement Directive No. 05 of the 12th Politburo on "Promoting the study and following of Ho Chi Minh's ideology, morality and lifestyle". It is no coincidence that the Politburo issued Regulation No. 144-QD/TW (May 9, 2024) Regulating revolutionary ethical standards for cadres and Party members in the new period; so that this elite

team has enough virtue and talent, capacity, qualities, intelligence, high prestige, equal to the task, ensuring the Party is strong in all aspects of politics, ideology, and ethics.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The article is researched on the basis of the basic principles of Marxism-Leninism, Ho Chi Minh thought, the guidelines and viewpoints of the Communist Party of Vietnam on revolutionary ethics, on Party building work; selectively inheriting the research results of scientific works related to the topic.

To assess the current status of applying Ho Chi Minh's ethical thought in educating and training revolutionary ethics for Party members of the Can Tho City Party Committee from 2016 to 2023; propose solutions for the period 2025 - 2030. The article uses a synthesis of scientific research methods including:

Historical - logical method: Used in the article to review and present the development process of applying Ho Chi Minh's moral thought in education and training of revolutionary ethics for party members of the Can Tho City Party Committee, Vietnam in a specific time and space sequence, in the relationship of mutual influence from 2016 to 2023. From there, generalize the research, find out the essential relationship, inevitability, and rules of issues related to the content of the topic; evaluate the achievements, limitations, and causes of the application of Ho Chi Minh's moral thought in education and training of revolutionary ethics for party members of the Can Tho City Party Committee, Vietnam in the period 2016 - 2023.

Analytical and synthetic methods: Used comprehensively in all sections of the article. On that basis, collect and exploit information from available sources related to the research topic, including original documents such as: Documents, resolutions of the Congress, statistics, reports and research documents of scholars in the past, providing findings and explanations on the contents related to the thesis topic.

Sociological investigation method: Is a method implemented using pre-prepared survey forms, aiming to assess the current status of applying Ho Chi Minh's moral thought in educating and training revolutionary ethics for party members of the Can Tho City Party Committee. The article surveyed 75 party members holding leadership and management positions; 565 party members not holding leadership and management positions. The content of the survey form includes general information about party members; on the current status of applying Ho Chi Minh's moral thought in educating and training revolutionary ethics for party members on: the role, standards, principles of training revolutionary ethics; methods of application, solutions to enhance application in the coming period. This information is presented through specific questions so that the surveyed party members can understand and answer fully.

Statistical, comparative and observational methods: Collecting statistics on data related to the current status of applying Ho Chi Minh's moral thought in education and training of revolutionary ethics for party members of the Can

Tho City Party Committee, Vietnam; Encoding and entering data using Excel software; Analyzing data, calculating statistical parameters, interpreting results using SPSS software. At the same time, there are comparisons, contrasts and observations of reality to ensure the reliability of the data. In the process of implementing the topic, the author uses a combination of the above methods to synthesize, compare, generalize, systematize, etc. to clarify arguments, evidence, assess the current situation, propose solutions to strengthen the application of Ho Chi Minh's moral thought in education and training of revolutionary ethics for party members of the Can Tho City Party Committee, Vietnam today.

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DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Basic contents of Ho Chi Minh's ethical ideology

Ho Chi Minh has many ways to explain revolutionary ethics. In his work *Revolutionary Ethics* (1958), he wrote, in summary, that revolutionary ethics is "determination to fight for the Party and the revolution all your life. Strive to work for the Party, maintain Party discipline, and implement the Party's guidelines and policies well. Put the interests of the Party and the working people above and before your own interests. Serve the people wholeheartedly. Fight selflessly for the Party and the people, be exemplary in everything" [10, p.603]. Revolutionary ethics is absolute loyalty to the Party and the people. "Revolutionary ethics is to blend in with the masses to form a block, trust the masses, understand the masses, and listen to their opinions" [10, p.609]. According to Ho Chi Minh, "For a good party member and cadre to become a true revolutionary, there is nothing difficult. It all depends on one's heart. If one's heart only knows how to work for the Party, for the Fatherland, for the people, then one will progress to a level of impartiality. When one is impartial, then one's shortcomings will become less and less, and the following good qualities will increase. In short, these good qualities include five things: humanity, justice, wisdom, courage, and integrity" [6, p.291].

In summary, President Ho Chi Minh's viewpoint on revolutionary ethics includes the following basic points:

First, loyalty to the country, filial piety to the people. Loyalty to the country, filial piety to the people are moral qualities that resolve the relationship between the individual and the Party, the Fatherland and the people. "Loyalty" and "filial piety" are standard concepts of old ethics (belonging to the Confucian ethical system), containing a narrow content of "loyalty to the king, filial piety to parents". Ho Chi Minh did not need to eliminate the old ethical concept that had been deeply ingrained in the perception and actions of Vietnamese people for thousands of years under the feudal regime, expressing the duty of subjects to the king, the responsibility of children to their parents.

Ho Chi Minh introduced into the old concept a new content, with scientific, revolutionary and humanistic significance: "loyalty to the country, filial piety to the people". This is a revolution in ethical concepts. The people, from being slaves, without freedom and democracy, became masters, creating history. Under the feudal regime, the mandarins were the parents of the people. Under the new regime, the people are the masters, and cadres and party members are the servants of the people. Being a cadre or a leader means being a servant of the people.

Loyalty to the country and filial piety to the people are the relationships between the country and the people, demonstrating responsibility for the cause of building, defending the country and the development of the country. The content of loyalty to the country and filial piety to the people is to be determined, whole-heartedly, whole-heartedly, and whole-heartedly serve the revolution, serve the Fatherland, serve the people; put the interests of the Fatherland and the people above all else, first and foremost. Must respect the people, trust the people, learn from the people, ask the people, understand the people, listen to the people's opinions, love the people, blend with the masses of the people into one bloc; grasp the people's feelings, hearts, and opinions; care about people's rights, people's livelihood, people's intelligence, democracy, and people's movements; make people trust, obey, and love. "Loyalty to the country and filial piety to the people" is not a slogan, must take work efficiency as a measure in the spirit of "complete every task, overcome every difficulty, defeat every enemy". That is truly the new morality, revolutionary morality.

"Righteousness means not being evil, it means being straightforward and honest. What is not upright and honest is evil" [11, p.129]. Ho Chi Minh pointed out: "You must be upright yourself first, then you can help others. If you are not upright but want others to be upright, that is unreasonable" [11, p.130]. Diligence, thrift, and integrity are the roots of righteousness. But a tree needs roots, flowers, and fruits to be complete. A person must be diligent, thrift, and honest, but also upright to be a complete person.

Ho Chi Minh believed that diligence, thrift, integrity, and uprightness are four virtues that humans must have, as natural as the four seasons of heaven

and the four directions of the earth. It is a measure of the quality of each person, because “without one virtue, one cannot become a human being”. Diligence, thrift, integrity, and uprightness are especially necessary for cadres and party members because they are people with power. If they lack conscience, they will have the opportunity to exploit and take bribes. Cadres and party members who have moral degradation will affect the reputation of the Party and the revolutionary mission. Party members who make mistakes will lead the masses to mistakes. Diligence, thrift, integrity, and uprightness are measures of the level of civilization and progress of a nation: “A nation that knows how to be diligent, thrifty, and upright is a nation rich in material things, strong in spirit, and a civilized and progressive nation” [11, p.128].

Diligence, thrift, integrity and uprightness are the foundation of a new life, of patriotic emulation, and are what is needed to work, to be a human being, to be a cadre, to serve organizations, classes and people, the Fatherland and humanity. Prime Minister Pham Van Dong said that, diligence, thrift, integrity and uprightness are characteristics of a prosperous society. The opposite is the characteristic of a declining society.

Impartiality is fair, impartial, unbiased, not for personal gain, doing things without thinking about oneself first, only knowing for the Party, for the Fatherland, for the nation, “worrying before the world, being happy after the world”.

Practicing impartiality is closely linked to fighting individualism. Individualism is “as long as you are fat, let the world be thin”; thinking about your own interests first in everything; only knowing “everyone for yourself” without worrying about “you for everyone” [12, p.66]. Individualism is a cunning, crafty thing, it cleverly lures people to go downhill. It is a very toxic germ that gives birth to hundreds of dangerous diseases such as embezzlement, waste, bureaucracy, greed for fame, profiteering, liking for position, power, etc. Individualism is a major obstacle to building socialism. Individualism is also a danger to the Party and the nation: “A nation, a party and each person, who were great and had great appeal yesterday, will not necessarily be loved and praised by everyone today and tomorrow, if their hearts are no longer pure, if they fall into individualism” [7, p.672].

Therefore, revolutionary ethics is to fight against individualism and other enemies in any circumstances. However, it is necessary to distinguish between individualism and the legitimate interests of the individual. Each person has his or her own personality, strengths, and personal and family life. If those personal interests do not conflict with the interests of the collective, then it is not bad. According to Ho Chi Minh, “fighting against individualism is not “trampling on personal interests”. And only in a socialist regime does each person have the conditions to improve his or her own life, to develop his or her own personality and strengths.

Being impartial means always knowing how to put the interests of the revolution, the Fatherland, the Party, and the people above and before personal interests. Only with impartiality can one have a clear mind to

wholeheartedly and wholeheartedly serve the people. Ho Chi Minh believed that one of the ways to consider life and the way to cultivate oneself of a revolutionary is to "maintain revolutionary ethics, the highest being impartiality" [11, p.290]. Ho Chi Minh clearly stated that a Party member must be honest, loyal, and enthusiastic. He must value the interests of the revolution more than his own life. He must sacrifice his personal interests for the Party. At any time, anywhere, in any matter, he must consider the common interests of the Party, must put the interests of the Party above all, first of all, personal matters and personal interests must be left behind; he must uphold the principles, strive to fight against erroneous thoughts and actions to consolidate the collective life of the Party, consolidate the relationship between the Party and the masses. Care for the Party and the masses more than caring for individuals, care for others more than caring for yourself.

Third, love for humanity. This is a moral quality that resolves relationships with others. Combining theoretical research with experiences, Ho Chi Minh believed that in this world there are only two types of people: oppressors and oppressed, evil people and good people, and two types of work: righteous and evil. Those who do righteous work are good people, those who do evil work are evil people. Ho Chi Minh once said: My love for people and humanity never changes. I love the good the most and hate the evil the most. That is the love that humanity has praised: "Wherever there is a fight for independence and freedom, there is Ho Chi Minh and the Ho Chi Minh flag flies high. Wherever there is a fight for peace and justice, there is Ho Chi Minh and the Ho Chi Minh flag flies high. Wherever people fight for a new world, against poverty, there is Ho Chi Minh and the Ho Chi Minh flag flies high" [13, p.90].

President Ho Chi Minh advised: "Every person has good and evil in their heart. We must know how to make the good part in each person bloom like spring flowers and the bad part gradually disappear, that is the attitude of a revolutionary. For those with bad habits, except those who betray the Fatherland and the people, we must also help them progress by making the good part in people bloom to push back the evil part" [7, p. 672]. In his sacred testament to future generations, President Ho Chi Minh advised the Communist Party of Vietnam: "There must be comradely love for each other" [7, p. 622]; every cadre and party member must always pay attention to love for people.

Ho Chi Minh's love for humanity is a shining expression of his absorption of Marxism-Leninism. According to him, "understanding Marxism-Leninism means living together with love and kindness. If you know many books but live without love and kindness, how can you call it understanding Marxism-Leninism?" That is a love not only within the national scope but also within the scope of humanity.

Fourth, the pure international spirit. This is the moral quality that resolves international relations: The international spirit is a moral quality originating from the nature of the working class and the socialist regime. President Ho Chi Minh was an ardent patriot, a great international soldier. He not only educated the pure and loyal international spirit but also embodied the spirit of proletarian international solidarity that President Ho Chi Minh raised in a verse:

"Throughout the mountains and rivers, we are one family/The proletariat in all four directions are brothers!" [14, p. 670], which is the spirit of solidarity between communists and oppressed peoples and working people around the world that Ho Chi Minh worked hard to cultivate through his revolutionary activities and through the revolutionary cause of the entire Vietnamese nation. It is also the spirit of solidarity, cooperation and friendship of the Vietnamese people with all progressive people around the world, for the goal of peace, justice, social progress and national independence.

Appreciating the role of revolutionary ethics, President Ho Chi Minh set out the criteria for a good cadre and party member, that is, a cadre and party member must be both talented and virtuous, of which virtue is the root. He himself is a shining example of revolutionary ethics, the crystallization of all the best qualities of the Vietnamese people and the noble communist moral qualities of Marxism-Leninism. The ethical rules that President Ho Chi Minh set forth have become a powerful spiritual weapon of our entire nation in the struggle for independence, freedom and socialism, for peace, cooperation and friendship with all peoples in the world. During the 55 years of implementing his Testament, Ho Chi Minh's thoughts on revolutionary ethics continue to be the torch that lights the way, leading the Vietnamese revolutionary cause, especially in the context of globalization, international integration, and the digital age.

The reality of applying Ho Chi Minh's moral thought in educating revolutionary ethics for cadres and party members at the Can Tho City Party Committee, Vietnam.

Realizing the importance of revolutionary ethics for cadres and party members, the Can Tho City Party Committee has paid special attention to thoroughly grasping and seriously implementing Directive No. 05-CT/TW on "Promoting the study and following of Ho Chi Minh's ideology, morality and lifestyle" and Conclusion No. 01-KL/TW of the 13th Politburo on continuing to implement Directive No. 05 of the 12th Politburo on "Promoting the study and following of Ho Chi Minh's ideology, morality and lifestyle" and Regulation No. 144-QD/TW (dated May 9, 2024) of the Politburo on Regulations on revolutionary ethical standards for cadres and party members in the new period. Cadres and party members in the Can Tho City Party Committee have strictly followed the teachings of "Diligence, thrift, integrity, impartiality and selflessness", improving the revolutionary ethics of party members; Self-cultivation, training to improve revolutionary ethics, eliminate individualism, uphold patriotism, national pride, absolute loyalty to the Fatherland, to the revolutionary cause of the Party; wholeheartedly serve the Fatherland, serve the people. Strive to study, strive and train, constantly follow the ideology, ethics and style of President Ho Chi Minh.

First, about implementing ethical standards of loyalty to the country and filial piety to the people.

In the context of unpredictable changes in the international situation and many fluctuations in the country, which have multi-dimensional impacts on the

thoughts, feelings and beliefs of cadres and party members, following Ho Chi Minh's moral ideology of being loyal to the country and filial to the people is more important than ever. The Can Tho City Party Committee attaches importance to educating and training the moral standards of "loyalty to the country and filial piety" for cadres and party members, in conjunction with the implementation of the Central Resolution 4 of the 11th, 12th and 13th terms on promoting the building and rectification of the Party and the political system.

Imbued with Ho Chi Minh's moral standards of loyalty to the country and filial piety, cadres and party members uphold the spirit of patriotism, love for the Fatherland, absolute loyalty to the Fatherland and the Party, wholeheartedly and completely forgetting themselves for the country and serving the people. When the COVID-19 pandemic broke out, with the spirit of "fighting the epidemic like fighting the enemy", "considering the task of fighting the epidemic as a combat task", cadres and party members in Can Tho city did not hesitate to face difficulties, hardships, sacrifices, and infections, with all their compassion, silent sacrifices, deep sharing, wholeheartedly serving, caring for, guiding, maintaining security and order for people in the epidemic area, guarding in quarantine areas, ensuring safety against the epidemic for people, participating in transporting goods, food, drinks for people, transporting sick people, etc. contributing their small efforts to repel the pandemic, building and developing Can Tho city to become increasingly rich, prosperous, and happy.

Being filial to the people in the current conditions means respecting the people, taking care of the people's interests, especially constantly expanding democracy to promote the people's strength. We must always put public affairs above private affairs, always refer to Ho Chi Minh's teachings: "Do good deeds, no matter how small. Avoid evil deeds, no matter how small" [11, p.131]. According to the survey results at the Can Tho City Party Committee, 100% of cadres and party members surveyed said that they are aware of respecting the people; love the people, trust the people, listen to the people's opinions, and wholeheartedly serve the people. This is clearly demonstrated during the period of fighting the Covid-19 pandemic; making efforts to contribute to life through volunteering such as helping the lonely elderly, supporting poor patients, distributing porridge, giving health insurance to students, cutting hair for cancer patients, and inspiring people with disabilities. Voluntary blood donation, for "A drop of blood given, a life left behind", "a heart of gold", "a heart for you", "When drinking water, remember the source, when giving fruit, remember the person who planted the tree", etc. Every Tet holiday, there are many "charity stops" to give out free food, mineral water, and cold towels, helping to ease the hardship and fatigue of many people on the long journey home for Tet. The generosity warms many people's hearts. Cadres and party members of the Can Tho City Party Committee consider taking care of the people's interests and benefiting the people as a noble goal in carrying out their political duties.

Imbued with Uncle Ho's teachings, being loyal to the country and filial to the people is not only the responsibility but also the morality of cadres, party members. Cadres, party members, and soldiers of the armed forces "are ready to fight and sacrifice for the independence and freedom of the Fatherland, for socialism. Any task must be completed, any difficulty must be overcome, and any enemy must be defeated" [15, p.435]. Have the spirit to fight and prevent negative things; practice the virtues of humanity, justice, wisdom, courage, and integrity according to Ho Chi Minh's thought.

Second, about properly implementing the teachings of diligence, thrift, integrity, justice, impartiality and selflessness.

Ethical education and training are necessary for cadres and party members according to Ho Chi Minh's ideology. Ho Chi Minh pointed out: Laziness is the enemy of diligence, and also the enemy of the nation. A lazy person can have a harmful effect on the work of thousands and tens of thousands of other people. "Remember: People have used sweat and tears to pay us during those hours. Anyone who is lazy is deceiving the people" [6, p.104]. Understanding and imbuing Uncle Ho's teachings, party members of the Can Tho City Party Committee have worked diligently, industriously, with a plan, creatively, assiduously, and must arrive on time, not late or leave early, achieving high quality and productivity. During his lifetime, President Ho Chi Minh emphasized: "Must be enthusiastic, persistent, and hardworking, at the same time be careful, clever, and gentle" [6, p.127], flexible, creative, and avoid being brave but lacking in strategy. Thoroughly understand and practice the ethics of Need according to Ho Chi Minh's ideology. Party members in Can Tho City Party Committee have a high sense of responsibility, really try and make efforts to promote their own responsibilities, seek progress in practical activities, especially in professional tasks as well as in studying to improve political level, improve professional level and expertise; actively fight against manifestations of laziness in activities, laziness in thinking, passive and mechanical studying.

The word "Diligence" in Ho Chi Minh's thought means intelligence, a necessary quality of cadres and party members. Ho Chi Minh taught: "If we want to wash away the evil traces of the old society, if we want to practice revolutionary morality, we must strive to study, cultivate, and reform ourselves to progress forever. If we do not strive to progress, we are regressing and backward" [16, p.284]. Understanding the teachings of President Ho Chi Minh, when asked about practicing ethical standards according to Ho Chi Minh's thought, over 99% of cadres and party members interviewed said that there has been a positive change in diligence and hard work in studying and working, working with a plan, being creative, and being determined in performing tasks. Self-cultivation, training, and self-improvement mean studying, training persistently throughout life, working with a plan, being creative, and working productively; and do not "Consider yourself good at everything, know everything" [6, p.295], do not "think you are good at everything, can do everything. You are better than everyone else in everything. You are a god, do

not need to learn from anyone, ask anyone” [6, p.631]. And realize that greed, bribery, corruption, and embezzlement are very shameful things, greedy, corrupt, wasteful people are guilty of crimes against the Fatherland, the country, and the people. Cadres and party members have actively cultivated, trained, and strived to truly become public servants, servants of the people, trusted, respected, and loved by the people. The saying of our ancestors is truly the truth “winning the hearts of the people, winning the world, losing the hearts of the people, losing the hearts of the people, losing the world”, and no force can defeat it.

Regarding education and training in practicing thrift for cadres and party members according to Ho Chi Minh's ideology. In the context of globalization, international integration, and a market economy, education and training in practicing thrift following Uncle Ho's example are of particular importance. According to a survey conducted at the Can Tho City Party Committee, when asked about practicing the thrift ethical standard according to Ho Chi Minh's ideology, 94.6% of cadres and party members answered that they have done very well and have done well in saving public assets, resources, and other material resources, saving money, effort, and time of the State, the people, and themselves. Regarding anti-bureaucracy and corruption, 74.4% of respondents said that there has been a change, of which 22.8% said that there has been a good change and 51.6% said that there has been a change [17]. The Can Tho City Party Committee has resolutely and strictly handled with Party discipline and State laws cadres and party members who have lost their moral character and moral integrity. From 2016 to 2023, the rate of party members who have fulfilled their tasks well is 90% or higher, the highest is 100% (in 2022); 80% to 90% of leading party members have fulfilled their tasks well and excellently [18, p.22].

Regarding education and training to implement the ethical standards of integrity for cadres and party members according to Ho Chi Minh's thought. A nation that knows how to be industrious and honest is a nation that is rich in material things and strong in spirit. This is especially meaningful in the context of globalization, international integration, and a market economy that is taking place vigorously with many temptations of material things, money, as well as the introduction of many foreign cultural elements, including lifestyles that favor enjoyment, luxury, ostentation, desire for power, etc.

Practicing the ethical standards of integrity according to Ho Chi Minh's ideology, integrity is a basic ethical value, a principle, a measure, a mandatory standard for cadres and party members, requiring serious practice of integrity to preserve the dignity and prestige of the Communist Party of Vietnam. To practice integrity according to Ho Chi Minh's ethical ideology is to be honest, educated and disciplined by law, from top to bottom, from bottom to top; because cadres and party members of agencies and organizations, high-ranking have great power, low-ranking have small power; whether big or small, having power but lacking conscience is an opportunity to "embezzle", an opportunity to receive "bribes", an opportunity to "use public property for private purposes".

He emphasized that cadres and party members must strive to practice integrity through specific actions, such as absolutely not using public property for private purposes, not touching a needle or thread of the people, etc. Buying and selling must be fair, borrowing something must be returned properly, and damaging something must be compensated. According to survey data at the Can Tho City Party Committee, the majority of leaders, managers and party members in the Can Tho City Party Committee who were asked said that they voluntarily cultivate and practice the virtue of integrity, build a culture of thrift, practice thrift, always keep themselves honest, fair, upright, clean, not greedy, not greedy for position, money, overcome the temptation of trivial material benefits and avoid extravagance, formality, not greedy for pleasure, not greedy for money, not greedy for flattery, not corrupt, wasteful, anti-waste. Be a role model, compete in practicing integrity, convince others with your own integrity and purity, be fearless when facing challenges and hardships, stand firm in the face of material and financial temptations and have created integrity in the people; "dare to think, dare to speak, dare to do, dare to take responsibility, dare to innovate, dare to face difficulties and challenges and be resolute in action for the common good" [9, p.42], worthy of the role of both a leader and a truly loyal servant of the people. The whole city of Can Tho has 2,328 collectives and 6,980 individuals who are typical and exemplary in education and training of integrity and morality according to Ho Chi Minh's moral thought, who have been commended and rewarded. Ho Chi Minh's revolutionary moral thought still retains its value in both theory and practice, is still relevant and full of humanity.

Chart 1. Studying and following Ho Chi Minh's moral example

Source: Author's collection

Regarding education and training to implement the main ethical standards for cadres and party members according to Ho Chi Minh's thought, this is an extremely important quality of cadres and party members. Ho Chi Minh said, "Diligence, thrift, and integrity are the roots of integrity. But a tree needs roots, branches, leaves, flowers, and fruits to be complete. A person must be diligent, thrifty, and honest, but must also be upright to be a complete person" [19, p.129]. This is especially meaningful in the context of international integration, market economy, and the implementation of following Ho Chi Minh's moral example, which is taking place vigorously with many temptations of material things, money, as well as a lifestyle of enjoyment, desire for power, luxury, ostentation, formality, etc. Lack of cultivation and training of main ethical standards leads to degradation, degeneration, "self-evolution", "self-transformation", and loss of purity. Can Tho City Party Committee is very interested in building the quality of the Righteousness. According to the survey results at Can Tho City Party Committee, the majority of leaders, managers and Party members interviewed answered that they are upright, honest, fair, do not rely on or avoid responsibility towards the people, do not fall into material temptations, are conscious of fighting against signs of ideological, moral and lifestyle degradation, always have a spirit of self-criticism; follow public ethics, be serious and always conscious of cultivating oneself with the revolutionary ethics of a cadre and Party member, cultivate talent with knowledge, convince others with their own uprightness and purity; practice "righteous culture" in work and in all aspects of social life. Regardless of their position, cadres and party members always fulfill the three tasks of "self-respect, self-respect, self-respect for work", not being arrogant, not flattering superiors, not looking down on subordinates, always having a sincere, modest, honest, united attitude, always putting national affairs first, before personal matters, not afraid of hardship, not afraid of difficulties, not afraid of danger, always working creatively, with a plan, carefully, working until success, not giving up. Passionately contributing to revolutionary ideals and beliefs, knowledge linked to practice, words going hand in hand with actions; spreading the value of integrity into the activities of the government, businesses, communities and all classes of people, contributing to building and developing the prosperous and strong homeland of Can Tho.

Training the ethics of impartiality. When promoting the spirit of impartiality, Ho Chi Minh is a shining example of impartiality. The Can Tho City Party Committee has actively educated and trained the qualities of impartiality for cadres and party members. Cadres and party members have imbued the qualities of impartiality according to Ho Chi Minh's thought. The survey results of the Can Tho City Party Committee show that the majority of leaders, managers and party members interviewed answered that they have scientific, democratic and principled working methods; clear distinction between public and private, not creating inconvenience or causing trouble for the people; cadres and party members dare to admit shortcomings and take responsibility; do everything thoroughly, not afraid of difficulties and dangers; always put the

interests of the organization and the collective first; Dedicated service to the people by cadres and party members in public agencies in accordance with the characteristics, situation, and political tasks of the agency and unit and in accordance with the functions and tasks of each cadre and party member; Resolutely fight against individualism, foreign worship, and pragmatism; eliminate the pursuit of fame and position, grab benefits for oneself, abuse power and position to appropriate public property, and gain benefits for family and individuals. Be frank, honest, protect what is right, protect the truth, protect the Party's guidelines and viewpoints. Resolutely fight against opportunism, laziness, hedonistic lifestyle, selfishness, saying things that do not match actions, saying a lot, doing little, saying one thing and doing another, being exemplary in diligence, thrift, integrity, impartiality, having the power to attract, spread, and exert good influence in agencies, units, and in society.

The Can Tho City Party Committee attaches great importance to self-education, focusing on cultivating revolutionary ethics of diligence, thrift, integrity, uprightness, impartiality, and selflessness, making those virtues deeply rooted and lasting, and imbuing and practicing revolutionary ethics of diligence, thrift, integrity, uprightness, impartiality, and selflessness as an example for the people and the masses to follow, spreading and having a positive influence in grassroots party organizations, in society, and among the people.

Third, about properly implementing the teachings of loving humanity, living with meaning and affection, and having a pure international spirit.

Practicing humanism, living with love and meaning. Loving people, living with love and meaning is an eternal beauty in Ho Chi Minh's moral standards. With Ho Chi Minh, a heart that loves the country, loves the people, loves the suffering, is ready to endure the highest sacrifices for the independence of the Fatherland, for the freedom and happiness of the people, love for people is boundless. Imbued with Uncle Ho's teachings on loving people, living with love and meaning, the majority of leaders, managers and party members asked said that living with comradely love for each other, compassion, altruism, tolerance and kindness, wholeheartedly for people, daring to commit to fighting evil, helps each person to progress and become better; having a spirit of community solidarity, being aware of helping others; respecting others, and behaving in a civilized manner.

During the Covid-19 pandemic, in Can Tho city, many practical activities of cadres and party members: "Charity bus", "Zero-dong market", "Rice ATM", "Emergency food support", "Protecting green areas", "Charity kitchen", "Can Tho city armed forces join hands for the poor - No one is left behind", "Exemplary, responsible, creative, effective, united, joining hands, unanimously with the whole people to prevent, fight and defeat the Covid-19 pandemic"; "City police force - Shield for preventing and fighting the Covid-19 pandemic - Sword to ensure security, order and social safety", "Golden heart fund, day for the poor", "war invalids and martyrs day", Tet for the poor, support for people with meritorious services, policy beneficiaries, the poor; support the construction of

great solidarity houses, houses of gratitude, love, etc. "Accompanying the poor" with 17,664,000,000 VND; donating 116 solidarity houses to localities, supporting livelihoods for 20 poor households with a total amount of 5.2 billion VND; supporting the "For the Poor" Fund for Nghe An province with 1 billion VND; "Trade Union Tet Market" donated 71,885 gifts with more than 26 billion VND, supporting the construction of 13 trade union shelters, etc. With the desire to share love and join hands for everyone. Just a small action but it has great meaning and value, contributing to helping each other in life and spreading these beautiful images to the community, contributing to creating the image of Can Tho people. Implementing President Ho Chi Minh's testament: Every good person, every good deed is a beautiful flower, our whole nation is a beautiful flower forest.

Fourth, on implementing a pure international spirit.

Pure international spirit according to Ho Chi Minh's thought. During his lifetime, when generalizing the most common standards of revolutionary ethics that cadres and party members needed to have, pure international spirit was also for the goal that all proletarians in all directions are brothers. In the context of globalization, international integration, the 4.0 revolution, in the digital age, the Can Tho City Party Committee promoted international cooperation in many fields of economics, science, education, agriculture, tourism, etc., "sending 183 comrades for overseas training according to Programs and Projects (such as Project 165 of the Central Organizing Committee); 90 cadres and delegates of the City People's Council, term 2016 - 2021, for training at Victoria Wellington University, New Zealand; 30 cadres participated in a short-term training course at the University of California, USA" [20, p.13], studying, working, and exchanging academic knowledge. The survey results at the Can Tho City Party Committee showed that the majority of leaders, managers, and party members interviewed said that they were ready to integrate internationally; aware of absorbing the quintessence of human culture; aware of international solidarity. "Consistently implementing the foreign policy of independence, self-reliance, peace, cooperation, and development; multilateralizing and diversifying foreign relations; being a friend, a reliable partner, and an active, responsible member of the international community; proactively and actively integrating comprehensively and deeply into the international community. Ensuring the highest national interests on the basis of respecting the fundamental principles of the United Nations Charter and international law, equality, cooperation, and mutual benefit; focusing on improving the effectiveness of international integration in the new situation. Vietnam is a friend, a reliable partner and an active, responsible member of the international community" [9, p.161].

Thus, in Ho Chi Minh's thought, diligence, thrift, integrity, love for people, living with meaning, and a pure international spirit are the soul, the culture, and have a strong influence in the country's political life, which cadres and party members must set an example to practice. According to President Ho Chi Minh, "Cadres who compete to practice integrity will create integrity in the

people" [11, p.127]. For that reason, President Ho always reminded cadres and party members to voluntarily practice diligence, thrift, integrity, love for people, living with meaning, and a pure international spirit in their work, in the use of state power, in self-cultivation, and in dealing with the people. These are the profound and profound teachings that he left for the revolutionary cause of our Party and nation.

Fifth, on implementing the principle of training revolutionary ethics.

Practice what you preach, set an example of morality. Practice what you preach to set a standard for people to follow, only then will it be convincing. Pioneering and exemplary, with the motto "above first, below last", "inside first, outside last", "party members go first, the country follows". The Can Tho City Party Committee has directed the dissemination and implementation of Regulation No. 101-QD/TW dated June 7, 2012 of the Secretariat on the responsibility of setting an example for cadres and party members, especially key leaders at all levels; Regulation No. 55-QD/TW dated December 19, 2016 of the Secretariat on a number of urgent tasks to strengthen the exemplary role of cadres and party members; Regulation No. 11-QDi/TW dated February 18, 2018 of the 12th Politburo; Regulation No. 47-QD/TW, Regulation No. 37-QD/TW of the Politburo on things that party members are not allowed to do, Directive No. 03-CT/TW of the Politburo on "Continuing to promote studying and following the moral example of Ho Chi Minh", Directive No. 05-CT/TW on "Promoting studying and following the ideology, morality and style of Ho Chi Minh", creating positive changes in education and training of morality in the whole society, cadres and party members have many movements that create a spreading effect, attracting the attention of all classes of people to study and practice the ideology and moral example of Ho Chi Minh.

According to the survey results at the Can Tho City Party Committee, the majority of leaders, managers and party members interviewed answered that they have done well in studying and creatively applying Marxism-Leninism and Ho Chi Minh's thought; said what they did; set an example in studying and practicing ethics; lived responsibly, had dreams and ambitions, dared to think and dared to do. The revolutionary ethics of cadres and party members do not come naturally, revolutionary ethics do not fall from the sky, but are developed and consolidated through daily persistent training and struggle, like jade that becomes brighter the more it is polished, gold that becomes purer the more it is refined, focusing on following through specific and practical actions and deeds, creating a strong influence and attraction for everyone to follow.

Implementing construction while fighting. Ho Chi Minh proposed measures to closely combine construction and fighting in the field of ethics. The Can Tho City Party Committee has focused on the principle of construction while fighting in educating and training revolutionary ethics for cadres and party members according to Ho Chi Minh's thought, and has used measures to closely combine construction and fighting, fighting while building, making cadres and party members clean, honest, and upright; actively fighting against bureaucracy, corruption, waste, negativity, factions, privileges, words that do

not match actions, taking advantage of one's position and power for personal gain; effectively preventing and repelling the degradation of political ideology, ethics, lifestyle, manifestations of "self-evolution" and "self-transformation" within the Party, associated with promoting the study and following of Ho Chi Minh's thought, morality, and style; Promote the responsibility of setting examples of cadres and party members according to the motto: the higher the position, the more exemplary one must be.

The survey results of the Can Tho City Party Committee show that 100% of leaders, managers and party members interviewed answered and fully participated in resolution study sessions, political activities, and seminars; fought against individualism, manifestations of ideological, political, moral, and lifestyle degradation, "self-evolution", "self-transformation"; fought against the pursuit of positions, power, power degeneration, and group interests; criticized, fought against, and pushed back the bad, the evil, and the backward, against wrongful views and behaviors that harm culture; fought against unethical and unethical views and behaviors; fought against wrongful views, distorted and slanderous arguments, and the "peaceful evolution" strategy of hostile, reactionary and opportunistic political forces living in exile to protect the ideological foundation of our Party and regime. Create strong, breakthrough, drastic and effective changes, increasingly going into depth, closely linking "building" and "fighting", protecting independence, sovereignty, unity and territorial integrity.

Implement lifelong moral cultivation according to Ho Chi Minh's thought. Can Tho City Party Committee identifies and recognizes lifelong revolutionary moral cultivation as an important task of cadres and party members. Party members regularly and lifelong cultivate and practice morality, lifestyle, revolutionary morality, uphold their responsibilities, always stand firm in the face of difficulties and challenges and are not tempted by material things, money, fame. The majority of cadres and party members have a correct understanding of Marxism-Leninism, Ho Chi Minh's thought, are steadfast in the goal of national independence and socialism, believe in the Party's Platform, guidelines, policies, and the State's policies and laws, strive to become cadres and party members with both talent and virtue, contributing to building and rectifying the Party, improving the Party's leadership capacity and fighting strength.

Cultivation and education of revolutionary ethics for cadres and party members in the Can Tho City Party Committee are closely linked to the building and practice of revolutionary ethics. The survey results at the Can Tho City Party Committee show that the majority of leaders, managers and party members interviewed said that they are conscious of cultivating ethics regularly and seriously, actively working, studying and working with a spirit of creative work, with high productivity, quality and efficiency; not extravagant, wasteful, ostentatious, formalistic; actively fighting against bureaucracy and commandism, as shown in: "They talk about democracy, but their actions follow the way of the mandarins. They talk about serving the masses, but they act

contrary to the interests of the masses, contrary to the motto and policies of the Party and the Government" [19, p.176], damaging the prestige of the Party and the Government; practicing thrift, cultivating, training self-awareness in studying and practicing revolutionary ethics throughout life; Upholding Marxism-Leninism, Ho Chi Minh's thought, firmly pursuing the goal of national independence and socialism, believing in the Party's Platform, guidelines, policies, and the State's policies and laws. Every year, 100% of grassroots party organizations develop plans and commitments to study and follow Ho Chi Minh's thought, morality, and lifestyle; 100% of cadres and party members fulfill their commitments to set an example, cultivate and practice morality, in conjunction with their functions and tasks [20, p.151]. Therefore, the issue of Party building in terms of morality, especially lifelong cultivation of revolutionary morality, is an important task of cadres and party members, wholeheartedly serving the Fatherland and the people.

However, reality shows that, under the impact of many objective and subjective factors, including the negative aspects of the market economy, globalization, international integration, the 4.0 industrial revolution, etc., a significant number of cadres and party members have degraded in political ideology, ethics, lifestyle, seriously violated Party regulations and State laws in performing assigned duties and tasks, violated the Regulations on what party members are not allowed to do and the responsibility to set an example; negative, accepting bribes, causing very serious consequences, committing crimes leading to expulsion from the Party, prosecution before the law, public outrage, very bad influence on the reputation of the party organization and local government. Particularly dangerous is the "rise" of individualism, fading ideals, faith in the Party, the socialist regime; a lifestyle chasing material values, disregarding spiritual values; Avoiding responsibility to the Party, to the Fatherland, to the people; using money from corruption to buy positions, regardless of integrity, morality, "not saving natural resources, raw materials" [21, p.160-174]. The worship of foreign values, valuing foreign values more than traditional national values, living dishonestly, unjustly, degenerately, and degenerately of those worms have reduced the people's trust in the Party, and will truly cause unpredictable disasters for the Party and the country. The revolutionary ideal has faded, and has been exploited by hostile forces to sabotage the Party and the State of Vietnam. Corruption has existed for a long time, becoming increasingly complex and sophisticated, causing ethical pain in the Party, seriously undermining the people's trust, and the survival of the regime. During the period 2010 - 2023, the Can Tho City Party Committee disciplined the party and the law severely punished dishonest people, disciplining 1,731 party members, of which 968 were reprimanded, 453 were warned, 81 were dismissed from office, 229 were expelled from party members and 08 party organizations, of which 04 were reprimanded, 04 were warned. The nation's moral values "gradually fade away or are gradually being eroded by foreign cultures and ethics" [22, pp. 39-44]. The awareness and action are limited, so it affects the formation of attitudes and behavior [23, p.719-737].

These things will really cause unpredictable disasters for the country, not only affecting the current young generation but also the future, and need to be urgently warned. Ho Chi Minh's Ideology on Training the Young Generation [24].

Chart 2. Party members who violate revolutionary ethics are disciplined

Source: Author's synthesis

The research results show that the application of Ho Chi Minh's moral thought in educating and training revolutionary ethics for cadres and party members today is both scientific and revolutionary and has profound dialectical characteristics. Ho Chi Minh's policy is to build revolutionary ethical standards for cadres and party members: loyalty to the country, filial piety to the people; diligence, thrift, integrity, uprightness and selflessness; love for people, living with love and meaning; pure international spirit. Ho Chi Minh's thought on revolutionary ethics of cadres and party members is the basis for the Communist Party of Vietnam and the State of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam to apply in building revolutionary ethical standards for cadres and party members in the context of international integration.

Applying Ho Chi Minh's moral thought in educating and training revolutionary ethics for cadres and party members of the Can Tho City Party Committee, Vietnam in the new period.

Ho Chi Minh's moral thought is the crystallization of the fine traditions of the Vietnamese people and the quintessence of human culture. Ho Chi Minh collected the quintessence of ancient and modern, Eastern and Western ethics, then inherited and applied Marxist materialist dialectics to sublimate all those human ethical values, thereby creating a new system of moral thought, Ho Chi Minh's moral thought. Ho Chi Minh's moral thought is a priceless spiritual asset of the Party and the Vietnamese people, a shining example for all Vietnamese people to learn and follow. Studying and following Ho Chi Minh's thought, morality and style is the most important solution in applying Ho Chi Minh's moral thought in educating and training revolutionary ethics for cadres and party members, which is both urgent in the new period and has long-term

significance for the cause of building and defending the Fatherland. To cultivate and train revolutionary ethics for cadres and party members according to Ho Chi Minh's thought, it is necessary to focus on the following main contents:

Firstly, implementing the ethical standard of "Loyalty to the country, filial piety to the people". President Ho Chi Minh is the most beautiful Vietnamese person, his entire life of 79 springs was dedicated completely to the nation, to the people. That life from the first moments until his heart stopped beating was only for the country, for the people, forgetting himself. When he had to return to the world of the virtuous. Ho Chi Minh only regretted not being able to serve the people longer, more. And his example of fighting for the country, for the people all his life for the cause of national liberation, social liberation, and human liberation, has been recognized and admired by the people of the world. A person "whose death is the seed of life and an eternal source of encouragement" [25, p.76]. Imbued with and thoroughly grasped the contents of patriotism in the new period; infinitely loyal to the ideal goals of the Party and the nation, persistently fighting to firmly protect the independence, sovereignty, unity and territorial integrity of the Fatherland, protect the Party, the State, the people and the socialist regime, actively participate in the implementation of the renovation for the goal of a rich people, a strong country, democracy, fairness and civilization.

Promote solidarity within the Party, national unity, maximize the sympathy and support of the international community; protect the national culture; maintain a peaceful environment, political stability, national security, social order and safety. Arouse the spirit, determination, will and aspiration to rise up, determined to overcome poverty and backwardness, make every effort to contribute to the country, build a prosperous and happy Vietnam.

Correctly resolve the relationship between individual - family - collective - society; the relationship between obligations and rights, with the spirit of striving to sacrifice for the common good, whatever is beneficial to the people must be determined to do, whatever is harmful to the people must be avoided at all costs; must put the interests of the Fatherland and the people above, before personal interests.

Respect and promote the people's right to mastery, we must always remember and follow his teachings on the invincible strength of the people, "revolution is the cause of the masses; must "take the people as the root". Because as Ho Chi Minh said: "being far from the people, not closely connected with the people, is like standing in the middle of the sky, certain to fail" [6, p.326].

Second, properly implement the teachings of "Diligence, thrift, integrity, uprightness, impartiality, and selflessness", upholding the dignity of the Vietnamese people. Be proactive in work, have a creative spirit, high productivity, quality, and efficiency. Must know how to be a devoted and loyal servant of the people, "worry before the world, be happy after the world", resolutely fight against corruption, waste, individualism, opportunism,

pragmatism, factionalism, and “group interests”. For leaders, managers, and party members, it is necessary to eliminate the habit of being ambitious for power, “term thinking”, chasing after fame, profit, position, and power, abusing power and position to appropriate public property, embezzle the State and people, and enrich themselves for their families, individuals, and localism; not be extravagant, wasteful, ostentatious, formalistic, or greedy for fame; know how to value the labor and assets of the collective and the people. Promote learning with a humble and inquisitive attitude.

Resolutely fight against laziness, indulgence, hedonism, selfishness, words that do not match actions, saying much but doing little, saying one thing but doing another. Party members must practice a private life of integrity and purity, not being arrogant or conceited; not flattering superiors, not looking down on subordinates; must eliminate the habit of chasing fame and fortune, reduce material desires; must put national affairs above and before private affairs and family affairs; “putting public affairs first”. Respect the Party’s discipline, discipline, and organizational principles, and correctly implement the State’s guidelines, policies, and laws. That is also the ideological and theoretical basis for the Vietnamese country to draw up guidelines and strategies for educating the young generation of our country in the 21st century to meet the requirements of accelerating industrialization and modernization of the country [26, p. 562-577].

Third, practice humanism, live with meaning and love. Ho Chi Minh always respected the people, wholeheartedly and wholeheartedly served the Fatherland and the people. He had immense love, a boundless love, tolerance and kindness for people. He said: “Each person, each family has their own suffering and the combined sufferings of each person and each family become my suffering” [7, p.674]. In Ho Chi Minh, love for people is a great and extremely sacred feeling. It is a manifestation of communist humanism, both holy and close, touching the hearts of humanity, for the common progress of mankind [27, p. 317-335]. As the late Prime Minister Pham Van Dong affirmed: Humanity, love for fellow countrymen, that is the deepest and best thing in President Ho.

Cadres and party members must have comradely love and affection for each other, helping each other to progress. Living together must be meaningful and affectionate, then it is called understanding Marxism-Leninism. Cadres and party members must truly love their compatriots, ordinary workers, the poor, those in difficult circumstances, “those who suffer the consequences of our leadership” [6, p.325]. Love must be transformed into action, promoting human capacity, intelligence, and creativity and for the people, making sure everyone has food to eat, clothes to wear, education, medical treatment, and housing. Implement democracy and social justice, harmoniously settle legitimate and legal interests recognized by law and society, create motivation [28, p. 282-298].

We must believe in the people, consider “the people as the root” with the awareness of having the people’s strength. We must absolutely believe in the

strength and intelligence of the people, no matter how big or difficult the task is, we can do it. Without that, nothing can be done. Ho Chi Minh taught cadres and party members that whatever is beneficial to the people must be done with all our might, whatever is harmful to the people must be avoided with all our might.

Fourth, uphold the spirit of pure and loyal internationalism. On the basis of ensuring the highest interests of the nation, on the basis of the fundamental principles of international law, equality and mutual benefit, both cooperation and struggle, consistently implementing the foreign policy of independence, autonomy, peace, cooperation and development; diversifying and multilateralizing foreign relations; proactively and actively integrating internationally; being a friend, a reliable partner, a responsible member of the international community. Uniting with other countries and peoples to protect the independence, sovereignty and territorial integrity of the nation. "Proletarians and oppressed peoples of the world unite". Today, in the objective trend of globalization, internationalism must have new content. Implementing international relations while upholding the principles of equality and mutual benefit, and non-interference in the internal affairs of other countries. For Vietnam, Vietnam integrates economically but not politically. Vietnam implements the principle that each nation has the right to freely choose a political regime suitable to the specific historical conditions of its people.

On the basis of steadfastness and creative application and development of Marxism-Leninism, Ho Chi Minh's thought must: "Implement breakthrough solutions to effectively prevent moral and lifestyle degradation, repel social negativity and social evils" [27, p.143]. Throughout his life of revolutionary activities, Ho Chi Minh always set a shining moral example of a revolutionary, wholeheartedly striving and sacrificing for the people, the country, and the nation [29]. Focus on "researching, supplementing and perfecting revolutionary moral values in the spirit of "Our Party is moral and civilized" to suit new conditions and the fine cultural traditions of the nation... Promote education and training in revolutionary morality, making each cadre and party member clearly see their duties and responsibilities, always steadfast in the face of difficulties and challenges and not be tempted by material things, money, and fame. Raise awareness of cultivating, training and practicing revolutionary morality. Strengthen the fight against anti-moral and unethical views and behaviors" [30, p.143]. Strengthen the leadership, direction, inspection and supervision in the management, administration [27, p.317-335]. "Build a political cultural, and ethical environment, proactively attack corruption, waste, and other negative factors throughout society" [31. P.113-123].

CONCLUSION

The application of Ho Chi Minh's moral thought in educating and training revolutionary ethics for party members of the Can Tho City Party Committee

still has many limitations: the method is still formal; some party members do not have absolute faith in the ideals of the Communist Party of Vietnam and strive for the goal of a rich people, a strong country, democracy, fairness, civilization, do not have the will to rise, the aspiration to contribute to the country of Vietnam; the negative side of the market economy, globalization, with the temptation and power of money has strongly and blatantly dominated, has been and will continue to cause the trend of commercialization: commercialization of power, commercialization of emotions, commercialization of knowledge, commercialization of moral personality, commercialization of traditional national culture, trampling on common morality, regardless of the law; there is still a group of party members who lack the spirit of solidarity, helping each other, "taking advantage of the situation", "generalizing"; lack of respect for everyone, jealousy, trampling on each other, uncivilized behavior. Particularly dangerous is the "rise" of individualism, selfishness, profiteering, insensitivity, inferiority, weakness, emulation, trampling, chasing after material values, disregarding spiritual values; education on "being human", ethics, lifestyle is still neglected; there is still skepticism and ambiguity about the goals and ideals of the Communist Party of Vietnam and the path to socialism in Vietnam; a few are confused, wavering, losing confidence; some even deny Marxism-Leninism, Ho Chi Minh thought and the Party's renovation policy. Therefore, applying Ho Chi Minh's moral thought in educating and training revolutionary ethics for Party members is a fundamental, long-term, and urgent task for a prosperous and powerful Vietnam./.

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